

Atomic oxygen erosion resistance of phosphorus-containing polyimides derived from Bis-(4-aminophenoxy) phenoxy phosphine oxide and aromatic dianhydrides

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Keywords: Polyimides; phosphorus-containing; Atomic Oxygen; XPS; Low Earth Orbit

Abstract

Bis-(4-aminophenoxy) phenoxy phosphine oxide, p-DAPO₄, was prepared from 4-nitrophenol and phenyl dichlorophosphate, followed by hydrogenation. A series of polyimides prepared from p-DAPO₄ and the corresponding dianhydrides by two-stage method was characterized by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (FTIR) and thermal analysis methods. All films showed 5% decomposition temperature range from 482 to 508 °C, and the char yields range from 49 to 66 wt%. In order to check the atomic oxygen erosion resistance of resulting phosphorus-containing polyimides film, AO exposure experiment was conducted in a ground-based atomic oxygen effects simulation facility with the Filament Charge and Bound of Magnetic Field (IFM). Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) and X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (XPS) were employed, respectively. The SEM results indicated that phosphorus-containing polyimide film **3a** showed a “relief-like” morphology after 20 h AO exposure. It is worth mentioning that the mass loss of **3a** or **3e** reduced to approximately 20% that of Kapton[®] HN film.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, numerous spacecraft are traveling in low earth orbit (LEO) altitudes, ranging from 200 to 800 km. Such as satellites, space shuttles, spaceships and space stations are being affected by atomic oxygen (AO), vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) radiation, thermal cycling and impact of small fragments et al.

AO can change the properties of the surface texture on spacecraft, thus the lifetime of spacecraft will be shortened [1-5].

Aromatic polyimides are widely used various aspects due to their outstanding properties such as thermal-oxidative stability, mechanical properties, high glass transition temperature and good resistance to solvents to our best knowledge.

Phosphorus-containing polymers are well known for outstanding flame retardant [6-7], good adhesive properties to substrate and low dielectric constant [8-10]. Incorporation phosphorus-containing bulk pendant into polyimides have been intensively studied. Based on knowledge on PPO (phenylphosphine oxide)-containing PIs, we can conclude that it should be an effective way to develop novel PIs by incorporating the P=O bulky pendant and asymmetrical units into the molecular skeletons of PIs. However, the report about AO resistance of phosphorus-containing is less except for NASA in the domestic and overseas. For this purpose, an aromatic diamine bis-(4-aminophenoxy) phenoxy phosphine oxide (p-DAPO₄) was synthesized first [11]. Then a series of polyimides were prepared from the condensation of p-DAPO₄ with various aromatic dianhydrides by two-step polymerization. The chemical structures, thermal properties and AO resistance of these polyimides are investigated.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Bis-(4-aminophenoxy) phenoxy phosphine oxide

(p-DAPO₄) was synthesized according to the reported procedure [11]. Pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA; a; Lonza Liyang Chemical Co., Ltd.; filmy class) and Benzophenonetetracarboxylic anhydride (BTDA; b; Shanghai Research Institute of synthetic resins; filmy class) were dried at 150 °C overnight before use. 3,3',4,4'-biphenyl-tetracarboxylic acid dianhydride (s-BPDA; c; Changzhou Wujin Linchuan Chemical Co.,Ltd; filmy class), Oxydiphthalic anhydride (ODPA; d; Shanghai Research Institute of synthetic resins; filmy class) and 2,2-bis(3,4-dicarboxyphenyl) hexafluoropropane dianhydride (6FDA; e; Institute of chemistry chinese academy of sciences; filmy class) were dried at 150 °C in vacuum for 8h prior to use.

2.2 Preparation of polyimides

Phosphorus-containing polyimides were prepared by reacting p-DAPO₄ with equal mole of dianhydrides (a-d). Polyimides syntheses are exemplified by specific synthesis of **3a** from the condensation of p-DAPO₄ and PMDA. The other polyimides were similarly prepared. To a 250 ml three-neck round-bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stirrer, nitrogen inlet, p-DAPO₄ 1.7816g (5 mmol), and CaH₂-dried DMAc 11.5g were added. After the monomer had dissolved completely, the reacting system was placed into an ice-bath and then cooled into 0 °C, PMDA 1.0906g (5 mmol) was added quickly and kept at 5 °C for 24 h. Then, the viscous polyimides solution poly(amic acid) was casted on glass by a doctor blade. The resulting poly(amic acid) thin films were dried at 80 °C (1 h) and imidized at 120 °C (1 h), 160 °C (1 h), 200 °C (1 h), 250 °C (1 h), and 300 °C (1h), respectively. The synthetic equations of polyimides **3a-3e** are shown in **Scheme 1**.

2.3 Characterization

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were obtained in the standard wavenumber range of 400-4000 cm⁻¹ by Nicolet NEXUS-470 spectrophotometer. Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) scans were conducted on a Perkin-Elmer DSC

thermal analyzer in a nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 20 °C/min to determine the glass transition temperature (T_g). Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed by a TA Q50 at a heating rate of 20 °C/min in nitrogen atmosphere at a flow rate of 60ml/min from 50 °C to 800 °C. 20 hours AO exposure experiment was conducted at Beihang university in a ground-based atomic oxygen effects simulation facility with the Filament Charge and Bound of Magnetic Field (IFM) (working air pressure 0.15Pa, discharge voltage 120V, and discharge current 140mA in the vacuum chamber). AO flux in period of 20h is 4.14×10²⁰ atom/cm². X-ray photoelectron spectra (XPS) were recorded on a PHI Quantera spectrometer with monochromated Al KαX-ray source to analyze the element component and valence variation of the film before and after AO exposure.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Infrared analysis of PI films

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of PI films **3a-3e** before and after AO exposure.

The FT-IR spectra of **3a-3e** are shown in Fig. 1. The characteristic absorption bands due to the vibration of the carbonyl groups in the imide ring are observed around 1781 cm⁻¹ (C=O asymmetric stretch) and 1722 cm⁻¹ (C=O symmetric stretch). In addition, the stretching vibration of C-N located at 1375 cm⁻¹ and the imide ring deformation at 723 cm⁻¹ further confirm the complete imidization of the PAA. The strong P-O-Ph absorption between 959 and 970 cm⁻¹ and the characteristic absorption of P=O around

1180-1200 cm^{-1} are observed in all spectra.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of polyimides **3a-3e**.

3.2 Thermal properties

Table 1

Thermal properties of PI films.

PI	T_g (°C)	$T_{5\%}$ (°C)	R_{w700} (%)
3a	236	504	63
3b	208	500	66
3c	183	508	64
3d	201	482	63
3e	215	492	49

T_g , glass transition temperature; $T_{5\%}$, temperatures at 5% weight loss; R_{w700} , residual weight ratio at 700 °C in nitrogen.

The T_g 's ranged from 183 to 236 °C as shown in Table 1. As expected, **3a** derived from PMDA anhydride exhibited the highest T_g (236 °C) 53 °C higher than **3e** derived from the most flexible ODPA (183 °C). This result is accordance with the rigid or bulkiness of dianhydride moieties (PMDA>6FDA>s-BPDA>BTDA>ODPA). Depending on the structure

of dianhydride, the 5% decomposition temperature ranged from 482 to 508 °C, and the char yields ranged from 49 to 66 wt%. When the open O=P-O chain decomposes at high temperature, the phosphorus-rich char retarding the degradation of the main chain of polyimides.

3.3 AO resistance properties

3.3.1 Mass Loss

The Kapton[®] HN film serves as a standard for relative comparison with the AO exposure films. All samples were exposed for 20 h with periodic removal and weighing of the specimen. All of the phosphorus-containing films exhibited excellent resistance (i.e. weight retention) to the AO. The phosphorus-containing films exhibited a non-linear mass loss over the 20 h exposure period. In contrast, the Kapton[®] HN film exhibited relatively constant, linear mass loss rate throughout the duration of the AO exposure. After 20 h of exposure, the mass loss of **3a** is approximately 20% that of Kapton[®] HN

film. It could be explained that An inorganic phosphate-type surface layer resisted to AO had been formed upon exposure [1].

Fig. 2. Mass loss *versus* exposure time during the AO exposure for the phosphorus-containing films.

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of PI films **3a** before and after AO exposure.

3.3.2 FT-IR analysis

It is clear that there is no obviously change before

and after AO exposure as shown in Fig. 3. The resulting could be explained that the surface of **3a** film give rise to new function group during the AO attack, whereas the depth of FTIR-ATR detection is about 5 μ m. The probe depth of XPS is approximately 7-10nm. Thus, the new phosphate-type layer aggregated on the surface of the film (nanometer range). However, the underlying structure are not vulnerable to damage caused by AO attack.

Fig. 4. XPS spectra P 2p of **3a** film before and after AO exposure 20h.

3.3.3 XPS analysis

The BEs of P element before and after AO exposure were compared, as shown in Fig. 4. The two peaks location at 133.6 eV and 134.7 eV assigned to O=P(OR)₃ before AO exposure, whereas the component peak at BE of 134.7 eV intensity increased after AO exposure. It could be explained that polyphosphate layer had formed on the surface of the film.

Table 2

The surface atomic concentration of the phosphorus-containing films **3a** and **3e** before and after AO exposure.

Sample	3a		3e	
	Element concentration (%)			
Element peaks	Before AO exposure	After AO exposure	Before AO exposure	After AO exposure
C1s	72.70	62.20	77.72	72.37
O1s	22.45	26.72	17.20	20.39
N1s	3.48	5.07	3.51	4.94
P2p	1.37	6.01	1.58	2.31

4. Conclusions

A series of polyimides have been successfully synthesized using p-DAPO₄ and the corresponding dianhydrides by two-stage method. These phosphorus-containing films exhibited better AO resistance compared to Kapton[®] HN film. These polyimide films exhibited T_g as high as 236 °C and 5% thermal decomposition temperature of 508 °C. These films exhibited a non-linear mass loss behavior, presumably due to the formation of a phosphate upon exposure to the AO. The outstanding properties make these films promising polymers for potential space application in LEO.

Acknowledgement

We thank the National Nature Science Foundation of China (No. 50803003) for funding this work.

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